

Clinical Study of Diabetic Foot with Different Treatment Modalities**Samay Singh**

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Abstract**Introduction:** Diabetic foot is complex, chronic wounds, which have a major long-term impact on the morbidity, mortality, and quality of patients' lives.**Material and Method:** Hospital based prospective study. 50 patients reporting to the Surgery dept. within study duration and eligible as per inclusion criteria will be included in the study.**Results:** Maximum 30% patients were treated through debridement of Diabetic foot whereas 20% patients received Slough Excision, Dressing & Skin graft and Toe Amputation as treatment modality. 18% patients were treated by I&D. amputation was the least used treatment modality.**Conclusion:** Diabetes Mellitus is a lifelong disease and diabetic foot complications can be life threatening, physically incapacitating, costly to treat and result in extensive morbidity.**Keywords:** Diabetes, foot ulcers, neuropathy.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is as old as mankind and perhaps humans know it from early ages. It is one of the most deeply studied disease and is still un-understandable ailment that human deal with. As we are digging deeper into the molecular basis of the disease mind boggling results are coming out. It is not a single disease but a constellation of diseases that it gives birth to i.e., the complications.

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by chronic hyperglycemia and disturbance of carbohydrate, fat & protein metabolism associated with absolute or relative deficiency in insulin secretion and/or insulin action.[1]

Diabetes is known for its micro & macro vascular complications like retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular & peripheral vascular disease. One of the most devastating complications of diabetes is 'Diabetic Foot' which is responsible for > 50% non-traumatic major limb amputations.[2]

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines diabetic foot as the lower limb of a diabetic patient that has the potential risk of pathologic consequences, including infection, ulceration and/or destruction of deep tissues associated with neurological abnormalities, various degree of peripheral neuropathy, vasculopathy and superimposed infection are mainly responsible foot ulceration. Ulcers which develop are difficult to treat due to poor wound healing which results from

a combination of neuropathy, ischemia, and hyperglycemia.

An inciting event such as unnoticed trauma through which micro-organisms gain entry, sluggish leukocyte response and high sugar content leads to destruction of proper host defense mechanisms which spread in subcutaneous and sub facial planes to the deeper tissues. Superficial ulcers are mainly colonized by staphylococcus aureus and/or streptococcus pyogenes while deep infections like osteomyelitis and abscesses result from a combination of aerobic and anaerobic micro-organism (gram positive cocci, gram negative bacilli like Escherichia coli, Proteus and Klebsiella asp. and anaerobes including bacteroids and Pepto streptococci.) [3,4,5]

Materials & Method**Study design:** Hospital based Cross sectional study.**Sample size:** 50 patients reporting to the Surgery dept. within study duration and eligible as per inclusion criteria**Inclusion Criteria:** All patients of Diabetic foot who gave informed verbal consent**Exclusion Criteria:** Diabetic foot associated with venous ulcers and lymphedema.**Assessment Tool:** Predesigned Pre structured questionnaire containing questions regarding

Clinical History, Demographic data, Risk factors for limb amputations and various treatment modalities was used.

Study Methodology: After obtaining permission of Institutional Ethical Committee and obtaining informed verbal consent from eligible study participants, all details of patients along with relevant investigational details were recorded in questionnaire.

Data analysis: Data thus collected were entered into excel and were then analyzed with help of

SPSS software through tables, diagrams and appropriate statistical test wherever required.

Results

In present study, maximum 52% patients belonged to age group was 51-70 years followed by 13(26%) in 31-50 age group, 3 (6%) cases in 0-30 age group and 8(16%) cases in more than 70-year age group. Male patients (78%) contributed to larger proportion of our study population as compared to females (22%).

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to site of lesion involved (N=50 cases)

Lesion	No.	Percentage
Left Dorsum of foot	3	6%
Left Toe	7	14%
Left fore foot	4	8%
Left plantar foot	2	4%
Left whole foot	5	10%
Right Dorsum foot	11	22%
Right Toe	4	8%
Right Fore foot	4	8%
Right plantar foot	4	8%
Right whole foot	3	6%
Right heel	3	6%
Total	50	100%

In this study, most common lesion was right dorsum of foot 11 (22%) followed by left toe 7(14%), left whole foot (10%).

Table 2: Distribution of Study Population according to Complications of Diabetes

Complication of Diabetes	No.	Percentage (%)
Cellulitis	16	32.0
Abscess	9	18.0
Ulcer	14	28.0
Gangrene	11	22.0
Total	50	100%

In present study most common complication of diabetes was cellulitis (32%) and least common complication was abscess (18%).

Table 3: Distribution of Study Population according to Duration of Diabetes

Duration of Diabetes	No.	(%)
≥10 Yrs	32	64.0
<10 Yrs	18	36.0
Total	50	100.0

Above table shows that out of 50 patients, 60% patients were suffering from diabetes for ≥10 years

whereas 36% patients were having diabetes for less than 10 years duration.

Table 4: Distribution of Cases according to Treatment Modalities

Treatment modalities	No.	(%)
B/K Amputation	4	8.0
Debridement	15	30.0
I&D	9	18.0
Mid-Thigh Amputation	2	4.0
Slough Excision, Dressing &Skin graft	10	20.0
Toe Amputation	10	20.0
Total	50	100.0

Table-4 shows that maximum 30% patients were treated through debridement of Diabetic foot whereas 20% patients received Slough Excision, Dressing & Skin graft and Toe Amputation as treatment modality. 18% patients were treated by I&D. amputation was the least used treatment modality.

Discussion

Wheel Lock [6] did a study which revealed that the youngest age with diabetic foot was 32 years, and the oldest age was 89 years. In the present study, maximum 52% patients belonged to age group was 51-70 years followed by 13(26%) in 31-50 age group, 3 (6%) cases in 0-30 age group and 8(16%) cases in more than 70-year age group.

When compared with Wheel Lock [6] series, there is not much difference in the oldest group, but the youngest patient was found to be 16 years younger than the compared study.

Mayfield et al [7] did a study on sex wise distribution of diabetic foot which included 32 males and 29 females.

In our study 60% patients were suffering from diabetes for ≥ 10 years whereas 36% patients were having diabetes for less than 10 years duration and same result were observed in Rawels et al [6].

In present study most common complication of diabetes was cellulitis (32%) and results were found in Bell et al [8] and diabetic research centre study (2005) [9].

In this study minimal stay in hospital was for the patients who had abscess or cellulites in which most common procedure performed was IND and debridement.

In this study, most common lesion was right dorsum of foot 11 (22%) followed by left toe 7(14%), left whole foot (10%).

Apelqvist et al [10] found that among the patients with diabetic foot 51% involved the toes, 14% involved the dorsum of foot and 9% involved the plantar heel. Reiber et al [11] found that 52% involved the toes, 11% involved the dorsum of foot and 18% involved the plantar heel. In present study maximum 30% patients were treated through debridement of Diabetic foot whereas 20% patients received Slough Excision,

Dressing & Skin graft, and Toe Amputation as treatment modality. 18% patients were treated by

I&D. amputation was the least used treatment modality.

In Collen et al [12] study 38.6% underwent amputation and in Osakakosainekin et al [13] 52% underwent amputation.

Conclusion

Diabetes Mellitus is a lifelong disease and diabetic foot complications can be life threatening, physically incapacitating, costly to treat and result in extensive morbidity.

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